

ASSESSMENT OF KNOWLEDGE AMONG PREGNANT WOMEN
REGARDING ANEMIA

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Pregnancy is accompanied by several physiological changes due to variation in hormonal activity in each trimester of the pregnancy. These changes are linked with the whole process of blood cells formation. Anemia, is a hematologic condition which results in decline of hemoglobin level below their normal range, is associated with pregnancy induced changes. It was seemed that lack of knowledge, malnutrition, poor parental care and low socioeconomic condition are contributing factors that leads serious health concern.

Aim: The aim of the study was to assess the level of knowledge among pregnant women regarding anemia.

Methodology: A cross sectional descriptive study conducted on pregnant women visiting primary health care units of tertiary care hospital in Lahore. The study participant were 164 pregnant women. A convenient sampling techniques were utilized.

Results: The analysis was done using SPSS version 21. The parameters were illustrated through bar charts and frequency tables. Out of 164 subjects, majority of the participant were between the age of 25 to 30 years, while their literacy level respectively are; 40 % up to matric, 39 % uneducated and only 20 % of the subject had higher education level. majority of the subject had lower level of knowledge towards treatment adherence in anemia 79.3%. Out of 164 subjects 98 participants do not know about hemoglobin, 68.9% female were not sure that anemia during pregnancy can be prevented by birth spacing.

Conclusion: The study revealed that most of the pregnant women had poor level of knowledge regarding anemia. Findings of this study also revealed that younger age, lower educational status has associated with the worst level of knowledge. this study emphasized the needs of an educational program, the goal of which is to focus on antenatal care, maternal health and primary health care to mitigate the burden of anemia in pregnancy.

INTRODUCTION

Background

Pregnancy is accompanied by several physiological changes, including hormonal changes, metabolic changes, electrolytes imbalance (Murray and Hendley 2020). These physiological changes result in low hemoglobin, a protein which makes about 90% of structure of red blood cells (Thiagarajan, Parker et al. 2021). Anemia in pregnancy is considered a major health concern in undeveloped nations, ultimately affecting morbidity and mortality parameters (Sharma, Kaur et al. 2020). Malnutrition, inadequate prenatal care, low socioeconomic condition, and insufficient knowledge about nutritional status in pregnancy, all these factors contribute to pregnancy induced anemia, which ultimately results in high rates of morbidity and death among pregnant women (Ramadhani, Syam et al. 2021).

Anemia is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a hemoglobin level <110 g/dl during pregnancy and 100 g/dl postpartum (Shi, Chen et al. 2022). A condition in which the concentration of red blood cells below from normal range, manifested by tachycardia, shortness of breath (dyspnea), paleness of skin, tiredness, and weakness, all these symptoms arise due to hypoxia (Ludwig and Strasser 2001). It is noted that the concentration of Hb decreased about 50 g/dl during second trimester of pregnancy (Díaz-López, Ribot et al. 2021). Anemia is not only the consequences of pregnancy, it may result from lack of awareness among women about anemia, inadequate diet intake and mal adherence of pregnant women towards therapeutic options (Gibore, Ngowi et al. 2021).

According to the World Health Organization, if prevalence of anemia is 5.0% or higher, then it is a public health concern (Elmardi, Adam et al. 2020). Occurrence of anemia than 40% in a population is considered as a severe public health problem (Sharma, Kaur et al. 2020). According to statistics, globally half of the population of pregnant women have Hemoglobin levels indicative of anemia (Kinyoki, Osgood-Zimmerman et al. 2021). In developed territories, the prevalence of anemia among pregnant women is 15% , while in developing countries, the prevalence ranges from 33% to 75% (Karami, Chalesghar et al. 2022). Higher

prevalence rates of anemia in developing nations is associated with multiple factors like socioeconomic status, lack of knowledge, individual perception, and lack of knowledge of nutritional requirement among pregnant women (Ali, Khan et al. 2020). While in Pakistan statistics of anemia in pregnant women is from $30-50\%$ (Khan, Rajput et al. 2022).

According to the above statistics of anemia in pregnant women as mentioned in Pakistan, there is a need to research this issue, in order to assess the knowledge level regarding anemia in pregnant women and to take appropriate action which will be required to eliminate anemia in pregnant women. The purpose of this study is to assess the level of knowledge regarding anemia among pregnant women visiting outpatient department of tertiary care hospitals in Lahore.

1.2: Problem Statement:

Anemia in pregnant women is a significant public health issue in underdeveloped nations. Anemia has severe consequences on health of both pregnant female and fetus. According to a study conducted in 2021, around 32 million pregnant women suffer from anemia. Due to the serious consequences of anemia for both women and their offspring health, this issue required to be highlighted in high scale.

Significance of the study:

This study will be helpful for health care workers, doctors, and nurses to pay more attention to teach the patient about the diet and the development of anemia due to lack of nutrition diet, especially among pregnant women.

Aim of the study:

The aim of our study is the assessment of knowledge regarding anemia among pregnant women.

Objectives:

To assess the knowledge regarding anemia among pregnant women.

Research Question:

What is the level of knowledge regarding anemia among pregnant women?

Operational Definition

Knowledge will be assessed through an adopted, modified and translated questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of 20 items ranging on nominal scale. The response to question are categorized as false, true and do not know. By using SPSS, each correct answer will receive 1 score, while question that will answer incorrectly or stated as 'don't know' received no point. The total score may range from 0 and 20, with higher scores indicating a higher level of knowledge. Likert scale will be used to scoring responses in the knowledge. Where score more than 75% considered good knowledge, 25-74% fair, and <25% will be taken poor knowledge.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Anemia is considered a serious health issue in pregnancy. Pregnancy is accompanied by several physiological changes, including hormonal changes, metabolic changes, electrolytes variations, all these changes has direct impact on the synthesis of red blood cells(Markoulli, Ahmad et al. 2023). Those pregnant women which pay no attention to their body overall health in pregnancy has a higher risk for developing anemia(Wawer, Hodyl et al. 2021). Proper knowledge regarding anemia in pregnancy and the utilization of knowledge properly may help in the prevention of anemia(Appiah, Nkuah et al. 2020).

In Al-Adhamiya a study was conducted with analytic component in primary health care centers(PHCCs) during a period of four months from December 2020 to April 2021. The purpose of which is to assess the knowledge level of pregnant women and to evaluate if there is any association between sociodemographic features of women and knowledge level about anemia in pregnancy. From the statistics, it was revealed that women had insufficient knowledge regarding anemia. The results concluded that 60 % of pregnant women has poor knowledge level regarding anemia(Al-Sattam, Hassan et al. 2022).

Similarly, from 3rd November 2019 to 30th January 2020, another study with descriptive component was

conducted in about six primary health care centers of Al-Amara city. The goal of the study was to evaluate knowledge of pregnant women related to the prevention of iron deficiency anemia, this study was more about treatment adherence and or iron supplementation in anemia. The findings of the study was shocking, about three quarters of the sample had poor knowledge (76.1%) regarding anemia induced by pregnancy, while the remaining women had a good knowledge, which was directly related to their educational status(AlAbedi, Arar et al. 2020).

A meta-analysis study conducted in Ethiopia, information gathered from different online data bases (PubMed, HINARI, EMBASE, Google Scholar and some of the African journals publish online. Pregnant women in Ethiopia were questioned about iron and folic acid supplementation and some of the comorbid factors that leads to anemia in pregnancy. Comparatively with the above study mentioned, the results of this study was contradictory, and knowledge level reported was 41.38% about iron and folic acid supplementation. However, high prevalence of anemia in pregnant women in Ethiopia may be due to others comorbid factors not highlighted in this study(Sendeku, Azeze et al. 2020).

Study on antenatal women was performed in Narayan Medical College Hospital, Jamuhar Bihar. Knowledge of those antenatal women visiting clinic at selected hospitals of Jamuhar Bihar was assess about anemia management in pregnancy. It was concluded that some of the participants had inadequate knowledge level 24(40%), while 34(56.66%) had moderate or acceptable level of knowledge out of 60(100%)(Gautam, Kumari et al.)

A cross-sectional study on pregnant women was conducted in Juaboso District, Western-North Region, Ghana. The purpose of the study was to assess knowledge level of pregnant women regarding anemia. Approximately 58.4% of women had low level of knowledge about anemia in pregnancy, which indicates the needs for implementing educational program to raise awareness in selected population(Appiah, Nkuah et al. 2020).

Hence the above mentioned studied confirm that majority of pregnant women had low level of knowledge regarding anemia. It was concluded that in pregnancy adherence to supplementation is

directly related to the level of knowledge female has about anemia. Lower level of knowledge among selected women is due to the lack of knowledge regarding pregnancy induced changes among pregnant women and adherence to supplementation. Thus the level of knowledge must be improved in pregnant women, in order to combat the serious health condition anemia among maternal mothers.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design:

A descriptive cross sectional research study design will be used.

Study Setting:

The study setting will be tertiary care hospitals of Lahore.

Sampling technique:

Convenient sampling technique will be used.

Sample size:

The simple size will be calculated through slovin’s formula.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where;

n= Sample size

N= Population size

e= Level of precision/margin of error

Eligibility criteria:

Inclusion criteria:

Our study includes those pregnant women visiting outpatient department of tertiary care hospitals of Lahore

Exclusion criteria:

Our study excluded pregnant women outside hospital, pregnant women in emergency department and non-pregnant women inside the hospital.

Ethical consideration:

The ethical consideration will be followed which is set by committee of nursing department, superior university. Participants will ensure for data privacy and they are not forced to participate in this study. Participants will be given enough information regarding study and their participation in this study. There will be no harm. Therefore, confidentiality will be maintained.

Data collection tool:

Data will be gathered by using an adapted version of tool to assess the level of knowledge regarding anemia among pregnant women.

Data collection procedure:

Data will be gathered from pregnant women those visiting to outpatient department of tertiary care hospital in Lahore.

Population of study:

Our study population is pregnant women visiting outpatient department in tertiary care hospital of Lahore.

Duration of the study:

The study will be take approximately 9 months.

RESULTS

Table No: 1 AGE Sociodemographic characteristic of study participants

Age (Years)	Frequency	percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
18 to 25	38	22.8	23.2	23.2
25 to 35	111	66.5	67.7	90.9
35 to 45	15	9.0	9.1	100.0
Total	164	100.0	100.0	

Fig:1

As shown in the above table and Fig #1, the frequency and percentage of participants with age group 18-25 years were 38(22.8%), Those with age group 25-35 years were 111(66.5%) and those with age group 35-45 years were 15(9.0%).

Table No: 2 Educational level of study Participant

Education level	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
☐ Uneducated	64	38.3	39.0	39.0
☐ Upto Matrics	67	40.1	40.9	79.9
☐ higher education	33	19.8	20.1	100.0
☐ Total	164	98.2	100.0	

Fig: 2

According to table#2, which show the frequency and percentage of study participant’s educational level. According to table, the uneducated participants is 64(38.3%), those who has educated up-to matric is 67(40.1%) and the frequency of participants with higher education level is 33(19.8%).

Table No: 3 Pregnant women knowledge scores about anemia

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	24	14.6	14.6	14.6
True	42	25.6	25.6	40.2
Do not know	98	59.8	59.8	100.0
Total	164	100.0	100.0	

As mentioned, the subject's response about anemia in table#3. Which indicates that most of the study subjects do not know about the correct answer. Their number and percentage respectively are 122(74.4%), while the small number of subjects respond correctly (true) is 42(25.6%) Out of 164 subjects.

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Table No:4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	46	27.5	28.0	28.0
True	69	41.3	42.1	70.1
Do not know	49	29.3	29.9	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

Fig: 4

According to table#4, which indicates the subject’s response to a question that “decrease iron in diet cause anemia”. The majority of subject respond incorrectly (false & don’t know). There responses respectively are 95(57%) and subjects who respond correctly(true) there number is 69(42.1%).

Table No: 5

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	81	49.4	49.4	49.4
True	42	25.6	25.6	75.0
Do not know	41	25.0	25.0	100.0
Total	164	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 5

A question about signs and symptoms of anemia were asked, the subjects response is mentioned in table#5. “General weakness and palpitation are not symptoms of anemia” approximately half of the

subjects respond incorrectly (true & don't know). There responses respectively are 83(50.6%). While some of them respond correctly (false) 81(49.4%).

Table No: 6

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	66	39.5	40.2	40.2
True	49	29.3	29.9	70.1
Do not know	49	29.3	29.9	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

According to the above table & fig#6, which show the subject responses to a question 'green leafy vegetables are not the source of iron'. The majority of subjects respond incorrectly (true & don't know). There responses respectively are 98(58%). Those who respond correctly (false) is 66(40.2%) out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 7

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	64	38.3	39.0	39.0
True	61	36.5	37.2	76.2
Do not know	39	23.4	23.8	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

Response towards question (5) indicates that, the majority of subjects respond incorrectly (true & don't know). There responses respectively are 100(61%). Those who respond correctly (false) is 64(39%) out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 8

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	53	31.7	32.3	32.3
True	57	34.1	34.8	67.1
Do not know	54	32.3	32.9	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

As shown in above table#8, the subject responses to question 6 “drinking tea immediately after meal can cause anemia”. The majority of subjects respond incorrectly (false & don't know). There responses

respectively are 107(65.2%). And those who respond correctly (true) is 57(34.8%) out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 9

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	33	19.8	20.1	20.1
True	95	56.9	57.9	78.0
Do not know	36	21.6	22.0	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

Fig: 9

Regarding general question about tea consumption impact on Red blood cells level which is “excessive tea consumption cause anemia”. Most of the women respond correctly (true). There responses respectively are 95(57.9%). Small number of subjects respond incorrectly ((false & don’t know) is 69(42.1%) out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 10

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	78	47.6	47.6	47.6
True	56	34.1	34.1	81.7
Do not know	30	18.3	18.3	100.0
Total	164	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 10

Question regarding Anemia impact on pregnancy outcomes “anemia does not affect pregnancy outcomes”. The majority of subjects do not know about the correct answer (false). There responses respectively are 86(52.4%). The number of subjects who respond correctly ((false) is 78(47.6%) out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 11

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	33	19.8	20.1	20.1
True	83	49.7	50.6	70.7
Do not know	48	28.7	29.3	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

Fig: 11
Anemia can affect fetal growth

Regarding anemia impact on fetal growth the participants response as shown as, approximately half of the subjects respond correctly (true). There responses respectively are 83(50.6%). The number and percentage of subjects who respond incorrectly ((false & don't know) is 81(49.4%) out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 12

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	51	30.5	31.1	31.1
True	62	37.1	37.8	68.9
Do not know	51	30.5	31.1	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

Fig: 12
Birth spacing cannot contribute in prevention of anemia during pregnancies

According to table#12, which indicates the subject’s response to a question that “birth spacing cannot contribute in prevention of anemia during pregnancies”. The majority of subjects respond incorrectly (true & don’t know) is 113(68.9%). Small number of subjects respond correctly (false) is 51(31.1%) out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 13

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	55	32.9	33.5	33.5
True	67	40.1	40.9	74.4
Do not know	42	25.1	25.6	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

Fig: 13

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	54	32.3	32.9	32.9
True	69	41.3	42.1	75.0
Do not know	41	24.6	25.0	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

Table No: 14

Regarding the prevention of anemia “ordinary local food is enough to prevent anemia”. Vast number of subjects respond incorrectly (true & don’t know) is 109(66.5%). Small number of subjects respond correctly (false) is 55(33.5%), out of 164 subjects.

Fig: 14

Regarding treatment adherence participant response as shown above in the table. Most of the women respond incorrectly (false & don’t know) and their number respectively are 95(57.9%). The number of subjects who respond correctly (true) is 69(42.1%) out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 15

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	47	28.1	28.7	28.7
True	76	45.5	46.3	75.0
Do not know	41	24.6	25.0	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

Fig: 15

As per table and fig#15, which indicates the participants response to question related to treatment adherence in anemia. 76(46.3%) subjects respond correctly(true), while other respond incorrectly (false & don't know) is 88(53.7%) out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 16

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	61	36.5	37.2	37.2
True	70	41.9	42.7	79.9
Do not know	33	19.8	20.1	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

Fig: 16

As per table#16, which shown the subject response to a question about routine follow up for anemia in pregnancy. The majority of subjects respond incorrectly (true & don't know). Their number respectively are 103(62.8%). While small number of subjects respond correctly (false) is 61(37.2%) out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 17

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	59	35.3	36.0	36.0
True	65	38.9	39.6	75.6
Do not know	40	24.0	24.4	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

Fig: 17
Routine screening for anemia should be done at least 3 times during pregnancy

Participant opinion about screening for anemia during pregnancy is shown in the table#17. Most subjects respond incorrectly (false & don't know). Their number respectively are 99(60.4%). While small number of subjects respond correctly (true) is 65(39.6%), out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 18

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	36	22.0	22.0	22.0
True	34	20.7	20.7	42.7
Do not know	94	57.3	57.3	100.0
Total	164	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 18

It is better to take iron supplement with orange juice to increase its absorption

As shown in above table and fig#18, the subject responses to question 16. The majority of subjects respond incorrectly (false & don't know). Their number respectively are 130(79.3%). While small number of subjects respond correctly (true) is 34(20.7%) out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 19

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	50	29.9	30.5	30.5
True	70	41.9	42.7	73.2
Do not know	44	26.3	26.8	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

Fig: 19

The subject response about best time to take iron supplement is shown above in the table#19. The majority of subjects respond incorrectly (false & don't know) 94(57.3%) out of 164 subjects. While remaining subjects respond correctly (true) 70(42.7%) out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 20

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	64	38.3	39.0	39.0
True	70	41.9	42.7	81.7
Do not know	30	18.0	18.3	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

According to above table#20, which indicates the participants response to question about treatment adherence about anemia. The majority of subjects respond incorrectly (false & don't know) 94(57.3%) out of 164 subjects. While remaining subjects respond correctly (true) 70(42.7%) out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 21

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	56	33.5	34.1	34.1
True	63	37.7	38.4	72.6
Do not know	45	26.9	27.4	100.0
Total	164	98.2	100.0	

Fig: 21
Iron supplement should be stop without doctor's consultation if you experienced side effects as nausea

As shown in above table subject responses to question 19. The majority of subjects respond incorrectly (false & don't know) 101(61.5%) out of 164 subjects. While remaining subjects respond correctly (true) 63(38.4%), out of 164 subjects.

Table No: 22

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
False	72	43.9	43.9	43.9
True	53	32.3	32.3	76.2
Do not know	39	23.8	23.8	100.0
Total	164	100.0	100.0	

Fig: 22
Compliance to medication intake of iron supplement is not essential in anemia prevention

About Compliance to iron supplementation when subjects were asked, their response is shown in the table#22. Most of the subjects respond incorrectly (true & don't know). Their number respectively are 92(56.1%). While the number of subjects who respond correctly (false) is 72(43.9%) out of 164 subjects.

A total of 164 subjects were present in the present study. Age of the pregnant female ranged from 18 to 45 years. The highest proportion of studied females (67.7%) was found in the age group 25-35 years. In our study (40.1%) of participants had Matric qualification, (39%) subjects were uneducated, and (20.1%) had a higher level of education.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of study population

Demographic Characteristics	Frequency(%)
Age of the Participants(Years)	
18 to 25	38(23.2%)
25 to 35	111(67.7%)
35 to 45	15(9.1%)
Educational Level of Participants	
Uneducated	64(39%)
Up to Matric	67(40.1%)
Higher Education	33(20.1%)

Knowledge Score

The present study revealed that highest percentage of subjects respond correctly (57.9%) to a question that excessive tea consumption can cause anemia, followed by

(50.6%) towards a question that anemia can affect fetal growth. The highest percentage of incorrect responses (79.3%) was to a question related to treatment adherence in anemia (it is better to take iron supplement with orange

juice to increase its absorption). Followed by (74.4%) towards a question that anemia is the hemoglobin level in the blood below normal. Approximately (68.9%) of female think that

birth spacing cannot contribute in prevention of anemia during pregnancies. About (59.8%) of female were not sure that anemia is the hemoglobin level in blood below normal.

Table 2: Distribution of the participants' responses about knowledge toward anemia

Serial Number	Knowledge Questions	Correct no(%)	Incorrect no(%)	Not sure no(%)
1	Anemia is the hemoglobin level in the blood below normal	42(25.6%)	24(14.6%)	98(59.8%)
2	Decrease iron in diet cause anemia.	69(42.1%)	46(28%)	49(29.9%)
3	General weakness and palpitation are not symptoms of anemia	42(25.6%)	81(49.4%)	41(25%)
4	Green leafy vegetables are not the source of iron	49(29.9%)	66(40.2%)	49(29.9%)
5	Not eating red meats, fish, and poultry for long periods does not cause anemia	61(37.2%)	64(39%)	39(23.8%)
6	Drinking tea immediately after meal can cause anemia	57(34.8%)	53(32.3%)	54(32.9%)
7	Excessive tea consumption can cause anemia	95(57.9%)	33(20.1%)	36(22%)
8	Anemia does affect pregnancy outcome	56(34.1)	78(47.6%)	30(18.3%)
9	Anemia can affect fetal growth	83(50.6%)	33(20.1%)	48(29.3%)
10	Birth spacing cannot contribute in prevention of anemia during pregnancies	62(37.8%)	51(31.1%)	51(31.1%)
11	Ordinary local food is enough to prevent anemia in pregnancy	67(40.9%)	55(33.5%)	42(25.6%)
12	Pregnant women should not take iron supplement if she is on healthy diet	69(42.1%)	54(32.3%)	41(25%)
13	Iron supplement should be based on doctor prescription	76(46.3%)	47(28.7%)	41(25%)
14	Missing routine visits to PHC centers does not affect pregnancy outcome	70(42.7%)	61(37.2%)	33(20.1%)
15	Routine screening for anemia should be done at least 3 times during pregnancy	65(39.6%)	59(36%)	40(24.4%)
16	It is better to take iron supplement with orange juice to increase its absorption	34(20.7%)	36(22%)	94(57.3%)
17	Best time to take iron supplement is before meal	70(42.7%)	50(30.5%)	44(26.8%)

18	It is enough to consume iron rich food once a week to prevent anemia	70(42.7%)	64(39%)	30(18.3%)
19	Iron supplement should be stopped without doctor's consultation if you experienced side effects as nausea	63(38.4%)	56(34.1%)	45(27.4%)
20	Compliance to medication intake of iron supplement is not essential in anemia prevention	53(32.3%)	72(43.9%)	39(23.8%)

Table: 3 Association between Sociodemographic Characteristics and Knowledge level of the participants

Variables	Knowledge level			Total(%) n=164
	Poor(%) n=58	Fair(%) n=57	Good(%) n=49	
Female age				
18 to 25	17(44.7%)	11(29%)	10(26.3%)	38
25 to 35	32(28.9%)	43(38.7%)	36(32.4%)	111
35 to 45	9(60%)	3(20%)	3(20%)	15
Education level				
Uneducated	23(35.9%)	23(35.9%)	19(29.6%)	64
Up To Matric	29(43.28%)	19(28.35%)	19(28.35%)	67
Higher Education	6((18.18%)	16(48.48%)	11(33.33%)	33

DISCUSSION

The purpose of recent study is to assess the level of knowledge among pregnant women regarding anemia. According to present study findings the total number of subjects was 164, majority of the participants were belonging to age 25-30 years. Their literacy level respectively is;40% up to matric, 39% uneducated and just 20% of participants had been higher education.

The present study depicted that most of the subjects did not know about the hemoglobin molecule and most of them was unaware about adherence towards supplementation in anemia. while previously the findings were similarly or contradictory to our study. In regard to the participants' response about questions in our study, the utmost portion of correct responses 57.9% was to the questions that says that excessive tea consumption cause anemia, followed by 50.6% to a question that anemia affect fetal growth (Mirzoyan 2014).

The highest portion of incorrect responses 79.3% was seen when the participants were asked about a question related to treatment adherence that is; iron supplement intake with orange juice increase iron absorption, followed by 74.4% to a question related to general knowledge regarding anemia that is anemia is defined as hemoglobin level below reference range. Out of 164 subjects 98 participants do not know about hemoglobin, 68.9% female were not sure that anemia in pregnancy can be prevented through birth spacing. Similarly, most of the participants (61.5%) believe that if a pregnant women experienced nausea while on iron supplementation, they can be stop without consulting doctor(Seyoum 2019).

In comparison to previous studies conducted on the assessment of knowledge among pregnant women regarding anemia in selected hospital of Peshawar(Pakistan). This study illustrated that majority of participant in Khyber Teaching Hospital, Hayat Abbad Medical complex and MSF hospital has

insufficient (poor) knowledge regarding anemia. From the statistics, it was found that 35% participants had weak knowledge, sixty one percent had acceptable or fair level of knowledge and about 4% had considered good level of knowledge regarding anemia (Arshad and Naz 2023).

While a study conducted in M Kuranga District, Tanzania shows that majority of the pregnant women 80% were anemic because of poor dietary practice, reflecting their low level of knowledge about anemia prevention and treatment adherence (Ngimbudzi, Massawe et al. 2021). These findings are consistent with the research from Malaysia, according to which anemia is more common among those women whose knowledge level are low or lack of awareness regarding anemia in pregnancy (Zani, Shahril et al. 2020).

Not only that a study conducted in Baghdad, the aim of the study was to evaluate Knowledge level about Anemia in Pregnancy among Females Attending Primary Health Care Centers, reported that most of the female in Iraq does not know that anemia is the low level of hemoglobin, and have a poor knowledge regarding adherence to supplement use in anemia during pregnancy. This study concluded that overall their level of knowledge was fair. Some of the factors that are associated with worst level of knowledge are; female age (younger), being single, low literacy level, unemployed, and low parity (Al-Sattam, Hassan et al. 2022).

Study from Iraq conducted by Senior and Najeeb in 2019 over 100 Iraqi women revealed that pregnant women knowledge about clinical manifestations of anemia was poor (98%). Similarly, about treatment adherence in anemia (87%), and has less level of information about foods that can prevent anemia, causes and complication of anemia in pregnancy. The study concluded that overall awareness was poor regarding anemia in pregnancy.

Another study conducted in the Cape Coast Metropolis, Ghana. The objectives of this study was to assess Knowledge, practice and attitude (KAP) of pregnant mothers regarding anemia attending antenatal clinic at the University of Cape Coast Hospital. The study reported that out of 225 subjects, utmost portion of the subjects (55.1%) had poor level of knowledge about nutrients that can prevent anemia. Results reflects that there is a

knowledge deficit among women visiting antenatal clinic at the University of Cape Coast Hospital, and emphasize on educational program to be conducted to raise awareness (Aleboko, Abdulai et al. 2023).

From India, Sri Manakula Vinayager medical college hospital, Puducherry, an institution based study was conducted. The objectives of which is to assess Knowledge, attitude and practices (KAP) of pregnant women regarding anemia, iron rich diet and iron supplement. The study highlighted that only 39.87% of the women were aware of and understood the term anemia. While 53.8% of the studied population belief that pregnant women were more vulnerable to anemia and 66.1% responded that health status of the fetus is affected by severe anemia. Some of the portion (32.6%) think that rather than directly taking iron supplement, pregnant women should focus on healthy diet in pregnancy. The findings of the study reflects that the subject had insufficient knowledge regarding anemia, iron rich foods and the importance of iron supplementation during pregnancy (Nivedita and Shanthini 2016).

In the present study, the mean total knowledge score was 19.1 ± 4.33 . The greatest portion of subjects has poor level of knowledge 35.8%, followed by 57 (34.8%) had fair knowledge, while the remaining 49 (29.9%) had good knowledge score. The distribution of Pregnant women by knowledge score and certain sociodemographic characteristics illustrated some association between knowledge level and age of pregnant female and their educational level. The portion of poor knowledge score was significantly at peak among the females who aged 35 to 45 years (60%), and had a lower educational level, Uneducated (35.9%) and Up to matric education (43.28%).

In reflection to the study mentioned above, the present study revealed that the majority of participants are not aware about iron supplement adherence in anemia, sources and most of them even had no knowledge about hemoglobin. Furthermore, two-third of a participants were not sure that iron supplement absorption rise when take with vitamin C containing diet for example orange juice. When asked about the source of iron approximately half of them of them were unaware.

Anemia during pregnancy required timely attention in order to prevent serious complications to both

fetus and affected mother. This should be done through the application of multi modal approach. There are numerous options to eliminate or control anemia in selected population, which includes raising awareness, preventive technique or supplements that should to consider in pregnancy and dietary modification. It is well understood that mother taking care of his health during pregnancy, may prevent upcoming offspring from serious diseases and at the same time it is beneficial for the pregnant mother itself.

Conclusion:

The present study concluded that most of the pregnant women had poor level of knowledge regarding anemia. Findings of the study also revealed that younger age, lower educational status has associated with the worst level of knowledge. Emphasized on educational programs, facilitating antenatal care, and actions to focus on primary health care (PHC) and maternal health is some of the strategies that can results in lowering the incidence of anemia in pregnancy, and will results in awareness about anemia in selected population.

Limitation of the study:

Due to cultural barriers, some of the participants were not interested in the study, that resulted in difficulty while collection of data.

Recommendations:

From the findings of the present study, it was seemed that lower literacy level directly affects treatment adherence about anemia in pregnancy, so thus it is enforced that;

Focus on primary health care services, by providing the selected population essential knowledge to aware them about the chronic condition anemia.

Conduct educational program for pregnant women, to enhance their dietary recommendation for anemia, family planning essential for healthy lifestyle.

Through the help of influential leaders, avoid any cultural barriers that results in any negative generalization about therapeutic plans.

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